

PRACTICES OF THE BULLIES AND THEIR ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 26

Issue 4

Pages: 408-417

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2475

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13909211

Manuscript Accepted: 09-10-2024

Practices of the Bullies and their Academic Performance

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the reasons why respondents engage in bullying practices among Grade seven and eight students at Talacogon Integrated School during the 2019-2020 school year. The school is situated between Lower and Upper Talacogon, Lugait, Misamis Oriental. Employing a descriptive correlation design, this study examined the correlation between two variables: the level of bullying practices and the academic performance of the respondents. The subjects comprised 35 identified Grade seven and eight students from Talacogon Integrated School. Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between respondents' level of bullying and their academic performance, as well as the significant relationship between respondents' profiles and their bullying practices. The hypothesis regarding the relationship between demographic profile variables (age, gender, grade level) and bullying practices revealed that while age did not significantly correlate with physical bullying, it did with verbal and social bullying. Similarly, gender showed no significant correlation with physical bullying but did with verbal and social bullying. Grade level, however, exhibited a significant correlation with physical bullying but not with verbal and social bullying. The researcher identified revenge, amusement, and feelings of inferiority as the main reasons behind bullying. The study found that the level of bullying practices in terms of verbal and social behavior, as well as academic performance, were within acceptable standards. However, the level of physical bullying practices was significantly correlated with academic performance, as the level of significance was lower than the standard value. Consequently, the researcher recommends implementing a teachers' training matrix for character formation to address bullying behaviors effectively.

Keywords: *practices, bullies, academic performance, descriptive-correlational*

Introduction

Bullying in schools is a growing concern of the teachers and community. It is one of the great concerns in the schools today, since it has a negative effect to students. Bullying causes many problems, not only for the victim, but also for the bully. Bullying will not exist if there are no bullies. The students who are bullies will likely to be hated and misjudged instead of understanding or finding out why they became bullies. The presence of bullies in various social settings, particularly within the school environment, raises significant concerns about the underlying factors driving such behavior. Understanding why individuals engage in bullying is essential for devising effective prevention and intervention strategies. While each case is unique, research suggests that bullies often grapple with complex personal and social challenges that influence their actions. These challenges may range from struggles with self-esteem and social status to exposure to adverse experiences such as trauma or dysfunctional family dynamics. Additionally, societal norms and peer influences can reinforce aggressive behavior among certain individuals, perpetuating cycles of bullying. By delving into the possible motivations behind bullying, educators, mental health professionals, and policymakers can address root causes and foster environments that promote empathy, resilience, and positive social interactions among all students.

In school at Talacogon Integrated School, many incidences happened of bullying among high school students. One of those observed were throwing stones to the other learners, spreading rumors, manipulating social dynamics, or coercing others to shun the victim, causing profound feelings of isolation and loneliness, making threatening gestures or facial expressions, invading personal space, or employing aggressive body language to intimidate and coerce the victim into compliance, and pushing and teasing the imperfection of others. These may result to disruption of classes and can make the learning environment not conducive to learning.

Addressing the problem of bullying in schools requires a comprehensive and multifaceted approach that involves collaboration among educators, parents, students, and community stakeholders. The House of Representatives promulgated an act to work hand in hand with the provisions of DepEd Order No. 40, s. 2012, or the DepEd Child Protection Policy on bullying, in achieving a better education in the country, entitled the Anti-Bullying Act of 2013, also known as Republic Act No. 10627.

Under the law, all elementary and secondary schools are required to adopt policies to address the existence of bullying in their respective institutions. Such policies shall be regularly updated and must include certain provisions as a minimum. One such provision is the prohibition of bullying in both school premises and in non-school-related locations if the acts in question create a hostile environment at school for the victim, infringe on his rights, or disrupt the educational process. A provision prohibiting retaliation against those who report bullying and implementing a system of anonymously reporting bullying acts is also required.

The aim of this study was to determine the level of bullying done by the bullies, their reasons for bullying, and the academic performance of the bullies. The study was conducted at Talacogon Integrated School in the first semester of the School Year 2019-2020.

With the above presentations, the researcher, being a teacher at Talacogon Integrated School, felt the need to conduct this research in order to minimize the bullying incidents at the school by helping the bullies in their character formation.

Research Questions

The main concern of this study was to determine the socio demographic profile of the bullies, the level of bullying practices of the respondents and the reasons behind the bullying practices and their academic performances at Talacogon Integrated School. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the socio demographic profile of the bullies in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. gender;
 - 1.3. grade level; and
 - 1.4. living accommodation?
2. What is the level of bullying practices by the bullies in terms of:
 - 2.1. physical'
 - 2.2. verbal; and
 - 2.3. social?
3. What are the reasons for bullying?
4. What is the academic performance of the bullies?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile of the bullies and the bullying practices?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of bullying practices by the bullies and their academic performance?
7. What teachers' training matrix on the character formation of the bullies can be devised based from the results of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

Descriptive-correlational study design was employed by the researcher. The bullies' age, gender, grade level, and whether or not they lived with parents or other family members were all described using a descriptive approach. The extent to which the respondents engaged in physical, verbal, and social bullying, as well as how well they performed academically. The association between the bullies' academic achievement and their demographic profile was determined by correlation analysis. Additionally, the connection between the bullies' degree of bullying behavior and their academic achievement.

Respondents

There were 35 identified bullies at Talacogon Integrated School. The respondents were selected based on the anecdotal record given by their advisers. The participants were composed of the following: 17 males and 7 female respondents from Grade VII and 11 males and 1 female respondent from Grade VIII. The researchers had then called each of the identified bullies and one on one interviewed was done.

Table 1. *Number of Bullies Participants by Grade Level*

<i>Grade</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>No. of Bullies</i>
VII	17	7	24
VIII	11	1	12
Total	28	8	36

Instrument

The study utilized a researcher-made questionnaire consisting of two sets of instruments. The first part focused on the demographic profile of the bullies, including age, gender, grade level, and living arrangements. The second part assessed the level of bullying practices among the bullies, categorized into physical, verbal, and social bullying practices.

For physical bullying practices, five statements were used: "I kick my classmates when I get angry at them," "I punch my classmates when we argue over petty things," "I poke my classmates whenever I want," "I throw stones at my classmates just to get their attention," and "I push my classmates whenever they're blocking my way." Verbal bullying practices were assessed using statements like "I insult my classmates anytime," "I tease my classmates whenever I can," "I tell my classmates about their flaws," "I trash talk my classmates for no particular reason," and "I use swear words when talking to my classmates." Social bullying practices were evaluated through statements such as "I spread fake rumors about my classmates," "I encourage others to turn against someone," "I tend to lead the group to leave someone behind," "I damage someone's reputation," and "I gossip about someone."

The Likert scale format was used for rating, with descriptors such as "Always" (4), "Often" (3), "Seldom" (2), and "Never" (1) provided for respondents to indicate the frequency of their behavior.

Additionally, the questionnaire included statements regarding the reasons for bullying, such as "Just for fun," "Want to provoke

someone," "Want to show superiority," "Wants to be recognized," "Being bullied themselves," "Fear of inferiority," "Wants to take revenge," and "Vent frustration to others." Respondents were asked to check the box next to the reasons they believed motivated their bullying behavior.

Prior to implementation, the instrument underwent pilot testing with 20 learners from grades 7 and 8, who were not part of the study's sample. The reliability coefficient of 0.84 indicated the instrument's reliability.

Secondary data on the academic performance of the bullies, specifically their average grades during the first grading period, were also collected for analysis.

Procedure

The researcher obtained permission to conduct the study from the school principal and teachers. All necessary communication and approval processes were completed, including obtaining signatures and approvals from the Superintendent, District Supervisor, Principal, Dean of Graduate Studies at St. Peter's College, and the thesis adviser.

Upon receiving approval, the researchers approached Grade 7 and 8 advisers to acquire the list of identified bullies through their anecdotal records. The bully respondents then completed the questionnaire during their homeroom activities, facilitated by the researcher. During the questionnaire distribution, the researcher assured the respondents of the confidentiality of their answers and guaranteed that no future references would be made based on the study's results. To ensure reliable answers, the questionnaire was translated into the vernacular for the respondents.

Additionally, one-on-one interviews were conducted with respondents to verify their answers from the questionnaire. For the academic performance data of the bullies, the researcher obtained their first-quarter average grades from their respective advisers.

Data Analysis

In this study, a combination of statistical tools was employed to analyze the collected data comprehensively and draw meaningful conclusions. Firstly, percentage was utilized to describe the demographic profiles of the respondents, including age, gender, grade level, and living arrangements. This statistical measure provided a clear understanding of the composition of the study participants.

Additionally, the weighted mean was used to assess the level of bullying practices among the bullies in terms of physical, verbal, and social bullying. This allowed for a nuanced understanding of the intensity of bullying behavior across different categories. Furthermore, frequency and percentage were employed to elucidate the reasons behind bullying behavior, shedding light on the prevalence of various motivations among the respondents.

The academic performance of the bullies was evaluated based on their first-quarter average grades, following DepEd standards, providing insight into their educational achievements.

Lastly, Pearson Product Moment Correlation was utilized to examine the significant relationship between demographic characteristics, bullying behavior, and academic performance. This statistical analysis helped uncover potential correlations between variables, offering valuable insights into the interplay between bullying behavior and academic outcomes among the study participants. Overall, the use of these statistical tools facilitated a comprehensive analysis of the data and enabled the formulation of robust conclusions in the study.

Results and Discussion

This section discusses the data that were shown in the tables and graphs. The data were analyzed, interpreted, and supported by related literature or studies.

Problem 1. What is the socio-demographic profiles of the bullies in terms of age, gender, grade level, living with parents and living with relatives?

Table 2. Profile of Respondents in terms of their Age

<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
12 years old	10	28
13 years old	13	37
14 years old	7	20
15 years old	3	9
16 years old	1	3
17 years old	1	3
Total	35	100

As shown in Table 2, profile of the bullies according to age revealed that 10 out 35 or 28% were 12 years old, 13 out of 33 or 37% were 13 years old, 7 out of 35 or 20% were 14 years old, 3 out of 35 or 9% were 15 years old, 1 out of 35 or 3% were 16 years old and 1 out of 35 or 3% were 17 years old, this follows the research of Sampson(2010) which states that bullying declined after the age of 15 evident by the percentage of bullies at the ages of 15, 16 and 17 years old. Furthermore, this also supported the study of Curwen et al,

(2011) which emphasized the peak of bullying which was 13 years of age.

Table 3. Profile of the Bullies in terms of their Gender

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	28	80
Female	7	20
Total	35	100

As shown in Table 3, profile of the bullies according to gender reveals that there are 28 out of 35 or 80% are male. And 7 out of 35 or 20% are female. Results indicates that leading number of bullies were boys. This is related to the study of Duncan (2004) that girls are prone to bullying. According to the researcher, the main reason of these phenomena is due to the societal perception of girls as the weak gender.

Table 4. Profile of the Bullies in terms of their Grade Level

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Grade 7	23	66
Grade 8	12	34
Total	35	100

As shown in Table 4, profile of the bullies according to grade level reveals that there are 23 out of 35 or 66% were grade 7 learners and 12 out of 35 or 34% were grade 8 learners. This is supported by McNeedly and Blanchard (2014) who estimated from 2000 child development center that approximately teen bullying appears to be much more common among younger teen than older teen.

Table 5. Profile of the bullies in terms of living with parents

<i>Living with Parents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	32	91
No	3	9
Total	35	100

As shown in Table 5, profile of the bullies according to living with parents reveals that there were 32 out of 35 or 91% are living with their parents and there were only 3 out of 35 or 9% are not living with their parents. This implies an issue of parental responsibility in dealing with abusive behavior as suggested by Nansel et al. (2001) who states that the trivialization of bullying is due to its normal occurrence in their household. Furthermore, lack of parental support may also provide a chance for a child to bully. As shown on table 5.1, profile of the bullies according to living with relatives reveals that there were 3 out of 35 or 9% of the respondents are living with their relatives. According to Brown (2008) children who lack emotional support from parents engage in bullying.

Table 6. Profile of the bullies in terms of living with relatives

<i>Living with Parents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Yes	3	9
No	32	91
Total	35	100

As shown in Table 6, profile of the bullies according to living with relatives reveals that there were 3 out of 35 or 9% were living with their relatives and there were only 32 out of 35 or 91% were not living with their relatives. Furthermore, lack of parental support may also provide a chance for a child to bully. As shown on table 1.5, profile of the bullies according to living with relatives reveals that there were 3 out of 35 or 9% of the respondents were living with their relatives. According to Brown (2008) children who lack emotional support from parents engage in bullying.

Problem 2: What were the levels of bullying experience of the respondents in terms of physical, verbal and social?

Table 7. Level of bullying practices of the respondents in terms of physical bullying

<i>Physical Bullying</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
PB1: I kick my classmates when I get angry at them.	3.43	Always
PB2: I punch my classmates when we argue over petty things.	3.36	Often
PB3: I poke my classmates whenever I want.	3.20	Often
PB4: I throw stones to my classmates just to get their attention.	3.49	Always
PB5: I push my classmates whenever they are blocking my way.	3.31	Often
Average	3.36	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As shown in Table 7, the level of bullying experience of the respondents in terms of physical bullying shows that the weighted mean average of 3.49 signifies that the bullies tends to do physical bullying like throwing stones to their classmates just to gain attention. The main reason behind this significance is the availability of the stones in the classroom. Furthermore, kicking their classmates whenever they get angry rank second with the weighted mean average of 3.43. It signifies their inability to vent out their anger productively. As observed, most of the respondents want to gain attention in order to gain validity as an existing individual in the classroom society. I found out that most for my students who engage in physical bullying have experience also physical bullying at

home and always expose in a violence environment.

Table 8. *Level of Bullying Experience of the respondents in terms of verbal bullying*

<i>Verbal Bullying</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
VB1: I insult my classmates anytime.	2.91	Often
VB2: I tease my classmates whenever I can.	3.14	Often
VB3: I tell my classmates about their flaws.	3.69	Always
VB4: I trash talk my classmates for no particular lesson.	3.29	Often
VB5: I used swear words when talking to my classmates.	3.23	Often
Average	3.25	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

As shown in Table 8, the level of bullying experience of the respondents in terms of verbal bullying shows that the weighted mean average of 3.69 signifies that in verbal bullying, most of the bullies tend to tell their classmates tell their classmate about their flaws. Based on my observation in my class, they always call my attention by saying mean things to their victims' just like, they point out about their classmates' flaws. I thought to myself that the bullies who bully their classmates want to gain attention and is very insecure for themselves because they too have their flaws and imperfection. I always remind them that it is not good to point out each other imperfection because all of us are not perfect.

As shown in Table 9 (Figure 9), the level of bullying experience of the respondents in terms of social bullying shows that the weighted mean average of 3.40 signifies that the bullies always encourage someone to turn against someone they don't like.

Table 9. *Level of bullying experience of the respondents in terms of social bullying*

<i>Social Bullying</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
SB1: I spread fake rumors to my classmates.	3.29	Often
SB2: I am encouraging others to turn against someone.	3.40	Always
SB3: I tend to lead the group to leave someone behind.	3.20	Often
SB4: I damage someone's reputation.	3.20	Often
SB5: I tend to gossip about someone.	3.12	Often
Average	3.24	Often

Note: 1.00-1.79, Never; 1.80-2.59, Seldom; 2.60-3.39, Often; 3.40-4.00, Always

Problem 3: What are the reasons why they bully?

As shown in Table 10, the reasons why they are bullied. This further show that 23 out of 35 or 66% bullied just for fun, 16 out of 35 or 46% bullied just to provoke someone, 19 out of 35 or 54% bullied to show superiority, 18 out of 35 or 51% bullied of wanting to be recognized, 20 out of 35 or 57% bullied because they themselves are being bullied, 22 out of 35 or 63% bullied because of fear of inferiority, 23 out of 35 or 66% wants to take revenge and only 21 out of 35 or 60% due to vent frustration.

Table 10. *Reasons why they bully*

<i>Reasons of Bullying</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
RB1: Just for fun.	23	66
RB2: Want to provoke someone.	16	46
RB3: To show superiority.	19	54
RB4: Want to be recognized.	18	51
RB5: Being bullied themselves.	20	57
RB6: Fear of inferiority.	22	63
RB7: Wants to take revenge	23	66
RB8: Vent frustration to others.	21	60

The results showed that most of the bullies engage in the bullying activities because they are bored and don't have any productive things to do. Base on my observation, the more activities given to these bullies the lesser the violence they're perform.

Problem 4: What is the academic performance of the bullies?

Table 11. *Academic performance of the bullies*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
75% - 80%	12	66
81% - 85%	15	46
86% - 90%	4	54
91% - 95%	4	51
Total	35	100

As shown in Table 11, the academic performance of the bullies reveals that there are 12 out 35 or 34% got 75%-80%, 15 out 35 or 44% got 81%-85%, 4 out 35 or 11% got 86%-90% and 4 out 35 or 11% got 91%-95% in their academic performance. The result showed that most bullies live with their parents, these means that parental relationships have no effect on their academic performance. Hence,

academic performance of the bullies and their family background has no causal relationship.

Problem 5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of the respondents and their bullying practices?

Table 12. *Correlation between the bullying practices and the age of the respondents*

<i>Bullying Experiences</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	
Physical	Pearson Correlation	.620	Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	35	
Verbal	Pearson Correlation	-.156	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.371	
	N	35	
Social	Pearson Correlation	.259	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.132	
	N	35	

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 12 shows the correlation between the bullying experiences and the age of the respondents. It reveals that there is a significant relationship between the age of the respondents and physical bullying experiences at .000 level of significance which is lower than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is not accepted. So it implies that most of the bullies who engage in physical bullying are the younger one. The more they get older, the lesser they comment physical bullying because they get to realized the wrong doing they did through the help of their teacher and the good people they met.

However the results reveals that there is no significant relationship between the age of the respondents and verbal bullying practices at .371 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Further, it also reveals that there is no significant relationship between the age of the respondents and social bullying practices at .132 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

It just shows that the bullies engage in verbal and social bullying regardless of their age. They can do it whenever they feel they wanted to.

Table 13 shows the correlation between the bullying experiences and the gender of the respondents. It reveals that there is a significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and physical bullying practices at .015 level of significance which is lesser than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is rejected. The correlation r value of -0.409 indicated a negative correlation which means that males are more bullies than the females in terms of physical bullying.

It also reveals that there is no significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and verbal bullying experiences at .248 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is not rejected.

Table 13. *Correlation between the bullying experience and the gender of the respondent*

<i>Bullying Experiences</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Remarks</i>	
Physical	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.409	Significant
		.015	
	N	35	
Verbal	Pearson Correlation	.201	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.248	
	N	35	
Social	Pearson Correlation	.136	Not Significant
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.436	
	N	35	

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

In addition, it also reveals that there is no significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and social bullying experiences at .436 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is accepted. So, the result shows that more boys engage in physical bullying than those girls and more girls engage in verbal and social bullying than boys.

Table 14 shows the correlation between the bullying experiences and the grade level of the respondents. It reveals that there is no

significant relationship between the grade level of the respondents and physical bullying experiences at 0 .174 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is accepted.

Table 14. *Correlation between the bullying experience and the grade level of the respondents*

Bullying Experiences	Grade Level	Remarks
Physical	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.235
		.174
	N	35
Verbal	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.547
		.001
	N	35
Social	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.329
		.050
	N	35

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

However, it reveals that there is a significant relationship between the grade level of the respondents and verbal bullying experiences at .001 level of significance which is lesser than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is not accepted. The correlation r value of -0.547 indicates that lower grade level tend to commit verbal bullying more than the higher grade level.

In addition, it also reveals that there is a significant relationship between the grade level of the respondents and social bullying experiences at .050 level of significance which does not exceed at the 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is rejected. The result shows that regardless of their grade level, they can engage in physical bullying whenever they wanted to. And some of the bullies are repeated so their grade level is not accurate in their age.

Problem 6: Is there a significant relationship between the level of bullying experiences by the bullies and their academic performance?

Table 15. *Correlation between the level of bullying practices by the bullies and their academic performance*

Bullying Experiences	Academic Performance	Remarks
Physical	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	-.379
		.025
	N	35
Verbal	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.234
		.175
	N	35
Social	Pearson Correlation Sig. (2-tailed)	.064
		.713
	N	35

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Table 15 shows the correlation between the level of bullying experiences by the bullies and their academic performance. It reveals that there is a significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and physical bullying experiences at .025 level of significance which is lesser than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is rejected. The correlation r value of -.379 indicates that the more physical bullying committed the lower their academic performance. It means that the more the bullies engage in physical violence, the lesser they strive in their academic performance.

It also reveals that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and verbal bullying experiences at .175 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is not rejected.

And it also reveals that there is no significant relationship between the academic performance of the respondents and social bullying experiences at .713 level of significance which is higher than 0.05 level thus the null hypothesis is not rejected. Furthermore, the verbal and social violence doesn't reflect their academic performance.

Problem 7: What matrix on teacher's training on the character formation of the bullies can be devised based from the results of the study?

Table 16. *Teacher's Training Matrix for the Character Formation to Bullies*

<i>Objectives</i>	<i>Activities</i>	<i>Persons Involved</i>	<i>Expected Output</i>	<i>Time Frame</i>
Counseling the bullies to improve self-awareness on what they have done wrong.	Character Assessment of the bullies, Psychoanalysis for bullies	Teacher, principal, bullies, guidance counselor, parents	Self-awareness on bad behavior and action against their victims	Whole year round
Conduct training for impulse control and anger management	Impulse Control Workshop for bullies	Teacher, principal, bullies, guidance counselor	Able to control different reaction with regards to different situation that can create bullying scenarios	Whole year round
Provide support system to reinforce behavior modification.	Peer support, mentoring, buddy and friendship approaches	bullies, guidance counselor, teacher	Will experience agreeable environment and will gain peer acceptance and security	Whole year round
To develop and reinforce firm rules and boundaries	Mental Health, Mindfulness for rules and regulation	Teacher, principal, bullies, guidance counselor, parents	Able to adopt and follow school rules and regulation and promoted order in the institution	Whole year round
To take responsibility on their own issues	Resilience training against personal issue for bullies	bullies, guidance counselor	Able to amend and resolves issues and conflict regarding the bully and their victims	Whole year round

Conclusions

The study concludes that bullying is prevalent among 13-year-olds, particularly males targeting females, with a preference for physical bullying, indicating a need for immediate gratification or attention. The impulsive nature of their actions reflects a lack of authority and social discipline, resulting in hostile behavior due to a disregard for consequences. Motivations for bullying include revenge, seeking fun, or attention from peers or teachers.

Regarding academic performance, a negative relationship exists between engaging in physical bullying and academic achievement, while no significant relationship was found for verbal or social bullying. Thus, physical bullying poses a greater threat to academic success.

Based on the analysis, findings, and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed:

Counseling sessions with the guidance counselor should aim to improve self-awareness and self-respect among bullies.

Teachers should establish clearer and more concise classroom management systems that promote appropriate consequences for inappropriate behavior.

Implement training workshops for bullies to enhance impulse control and anger management skills.

Provide training for bullies on problem-solving and social skills.

Utilize a Character Formation Matrix for Bullies as a tool for behavioral improvement.

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